

ON THE USE OF MESH MORPHING TECHNIQUES IN REDUCED ORDER MODELS FOR THE STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS OF GEOMETRICALLY MISTUNED BLISKS

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ABSTRACT

A technique is proposed to overcome computational issues caused by the use of multiple meshes in reduced order models (ROMs) for the structural dynamics of mistuned blisks. Due to the need for repairs (blends) or geometric changes during design iterations, models often require the use of distinct meshes for the same component. Most ROMs for such cases start from pristine modal information, which must be obtained for every mesh involved. Due to the nature of normal modes in cyclic structures, a first challenge arises with respect to their correct clocking, or alignment. Modes have arbitrary clocking for cyclic symmetric systems, and hence modes are potentially different for different meshes. In addition to this, imperfect clocking and cyclic interface compatibility can strongly affect the accuracy of the predicted response. This paper presents a method to preserve the accuracy of ROMs and at the same time reduce the computational overhead associated with the presence of multiple morphed meshes. Numerical issues associated with the presence of multiple meshes and sets of modes are investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, the increase in computational capabilities has led to an increased use of simulation in design. The use of different meshes or of mesh morphing techniques is very common in the design process. Mesh morphing in structural dynamics is particularly useful thanks to its ability to transform existing meshes without requiring a completely new mesh every time the design is changed. Thus, evaluating and optimizing multiple designs can be accomplished with savings in both computational time and cost. Many examples can be found in both the automotive and aerospace fields [1,2], and in many other fields [3–5] too. The design optimization can also be carried out using reduced order models (ROMs) when the full order solution is too expensive computationally.

When it comes to cyclic symmetric structures, such as the ones found in turbomachinery, other challenges arise. The dynamics of cyclic structures can be substantially altered by the presence of mistuning [6], i.e. any noncyclic deviation from the nominal system. Perfect symmetry is unattainable in real structures, and hence mistuning is always present. Thus, cyclic predictions are not always accurate, and full-wheel analyses must be carried out. This leads to a substantial increase in the required computational cost associated with the solution of the full order model (FOM). For this reason, the use of ROMs is important. When geometric changes are large, as is the case in the presence of blends (e.g., repairs applied to some of the sectors), advanced mesh morphing techniques can be used to ensure that the finite element (FE) model accurately represents the blended geometry and maintains mesh quality (e.g., it does not result in coarsely represented surfaces). The morphing process must be carried out for each geometrically mistuned blade in the assembly, resulting in a system that potentially has as many different sector meshes as the number of sectors.

Several techniques have been proposed for the study of the structural dynamics of geometrically mistuned blisks [7–12]. However, only few studies focus on the issues that may arise when using multiple meshes, such as mode clocking, interface compatibility, and projection errors. The issue of mode clocking is discussed in detail in [7], where a solution to deal with small geometric mistuning is proposed. However, the small mistuning assumption does not hold for large blends, such as the one shown in Figure 1, where it can be seen that the morphed and the pristine un-morphed sectors have substantially different FE node numbers and topologies. In that case, not only the clocking might affect the results, but also the mesh compatibility at the (disk) interface between sectors. This compatibility can be expressed as a set of constraints on node pairs requiring them to experience the same motion [10]. This becomes a significant challenge especially when acceleration modes

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are used, like in the case of the MAX method [9]. Furthermore, the method used in [9] involves the calculation of multiple sets of pristine modes, which requires significant computational time. Another drawback of the methods mentioned above is that they only deal with meshes having the same number of nodes. This is not always the case, as mesh refinement might be necessary in regions that are highly morphed. Thus, it is not efficient to use the methods presented in [7,10].

A method able to tackle both interface compatibility and clocking issues for the calculation of pristine morphed normal modes is proposed in this paper. Consider an initial (pristine) mesh which has been morphed in various ways to model various blending geometries. The proposed approach is able to avoid the need to solve eigenvalue problems of high computational cost in the process of calculating normal modes for each new/morphed mesh. Instead, the technique proposed exploits the fact that most of the nodes of the new meshes maintain their original (pristine) physical location in the blisk. This is also true of the interface nodes. These nodes cannot be moved because mesh compatibility has to be enforced between morphed and un-morphed parts of the model. Thus, modal information is already available for those nodes, and need not be re-calculated. For the set of nodes that do not have a one-to-one mapping to the original ones, the modal displacement is obtained by solving a forced response problem that only affects that set of nodes. As a result, the computational cost is substantially reduced, while correct clocking and compatibility are implicitly enforced. The new method outperforms others in the literature in terms of speed and memory requirements, as it reduces both the number of computations required and the problem dimensionality. The method is validated by comparing ROM results with full order model results.

NOMENCLATURE

i	Sector index
j	Mesh type index
$\mathbf{u}^j, \bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$	Orthogonal mode pair basis for mesh j
$\Phi^j, \bar{\Phi}^j$	System cyclic modes from the j^{th} mesh
$\hat{\Phi}, \hat{\bar{\Phi}}$	System non-cyclic modes
${}_i\Phi^j, {}_i\bar{\Phi}^j$	Sector i component of a pair of cyclic modes from the j^{th} mesh
\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{K}	Mass and stiffness matrices of the cyclic symmetric system
$\hat{\mathbf{M}}, \hat{\mathbf{K}}$	Mass and stiffness matrices of the non-cyclic symmetric system
${}_i\mathbf{M}^j, {}_i\mathbf{K}^j$	Sector i mass and stiffness matrices from the j^{th} mesh
$\hat{\mu}, \hat{k}$	ROM mass and stiffness matrices
N	Number of blades
\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{q}	Physical and modal displacement
ω	Natural frequency
\mathbf{F}	Vector of external forces
\mathbf{f}	ROM vector of external forces

BACKGROUND

The equations of motion (EOMs) for the structural dynamics of a mechanical structure can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}\ddot{\mathbf{x}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{F}, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ is the mass matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ is the stiffness matrix, \mathbf{x} is the vector of physical degrees of freedom (DOFs), and \mathbf{F} is the vector of external forces. In this paper, we focus on nominally cyclic symmetric structures like blisks, which are composed of several sectors that can have different morphed meshes. The presence of multiple meshes or mistuning makes the system lose cyclic symmetry properties. As a result, particular care must be taken when handling system modes and matrices.

Let us consider the case of a cyclic symmetric system having identical meshes in all the sectors. Due to the symmetry of the system, it is computationally efficient and convenient to express global quantities like mass and stiffness matrices using single sector quantities. In particular, the mass and stiffness matrices \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} of the entire pristine structure can be conveniently written in block diagonal form, as

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}^j & \mathbf{0} & \ddots \\ \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \ddots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{M}^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}^j & \mathbf{0} & \ddots \\ \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \ddots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{M}^j and \mathbf{K}^j represent the mass and stiffness matrices of the pristine sector, obtained with free-interface boundary conditions at the interfaces between sectors, and duplicate nodes at those interfaces. A pristine sector is a sector of the nominal physical structure. A pristine sector can be discretized with different meshes, as shown in Figure 1a and Figure 1c. Thus, there can be multiple pristine morphed meshes, and multiple pristine modes. They all represent the same physical structure and the same physical modes, but using different meshes.

Superscript j indicates the mesh index. All sector level matrices are identical when all sectors have the same mesh. Mesh $j = 0$ is the one that has not been morphed, and it is used as baseline. Mesh $j = 0$ is referred to as the un-morphed mesh.

For a mistuned system, or a system with distinct meshes in every sector, the mass and stiffness matrices of the blisk can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}} = \begin{bmatrix} {}_1\mathbf{M}^{m(1)} & \mathbf{0} & \ddots \\ \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \ddots & \mathbf{0} & {}_N\mathbf{M}^{m(N)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} {}_1\mathbf{K}^{m(1)} & \mathbf{0} & \ddots \\ \mathbf{0} & \ddots & \mathbf{0} \\ \ddots & \mathbf{0} & {}_N\mathbf{K}^{m(N)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where ${}_i\mathbf{M}^{m(i)}$ and ${}_i\mathbf{K}^{m(i)}$ represent the sector level mass and stiffness matrices of the i^{th} sector, calculated on the

$m(i)^{\text{th}}$ mesh. The mapping function $m(i)$ maps the sector index i to the corresponding mesh. Please note that a pristine system having multiple meshes (distinct in distinct sectors) is not cyclic computationally because the system matrices do not have a block circulant structure [13].

When a structure has cyclic symmetry with mesh j in all its sectors, its modes can be grouped according to their nodal diameters, and the response of the entire system can be obtained using a single sector [14]. In particular, modes appear as a single mode, or as a pair of orthogonal modes depending on the nodal diameter. To express them in terms of single sector quantities, modes Φ^j , $\bar{\Phi}^j$ of the entire structure can be partitioned as

$$\Phi^j = \begin{bmatrix} 1\Phi^j \\ \vdots \\ N\Phi^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\Phi}^j = \begin{bmatrix} 1\bar{\Phi}^j \\ \vdots \\ N\bar{\Phi}^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where ${}_i\Phi^j$ and ${}_i\bar{\Phi}^j$ represent the portion of the modes corresponding to the i^{th} sector for mesh j .

Let us now consider the case of a pristine blisk having different meshes in different sectors. Such a system can be described using matrices \hat{M} and \hat{K} from Eqns. (4) and (5). The modes of such a system can be written as

$$\hat{\Phi} = \begin{bmatrix} 1\hat{\Phi}^{m(1)} \\ \vdots \\ N\hat{\Phi}^{m(N)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\bar{\Phi}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1\hat{\bar{\Phi}}^{m(1)} \\ \vdots \\ N\hat{\bar{\Phi}}^{m(N)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where ${}_i\hat{\Phi}^{m(i)}$ and ${}_i\hat{\bar{\Phi}}^{m(i)}$ are the i^{th} sector portion of the modes, obtained using the $m(i)^{\text{th}}$ mesh. The modes $\hat{\Phi}$ and $\hat{\bar{\Phi}}$ differ from the ones introduced in Eqn. (6) because they are composed of sector modes coming from different meshes. Please note that if the meshes are converged and pristine, then matrices $\hat{\Phi}$ and Φ^j represent the same physical modes, but sampled at different locations.

A ROM can be built by projecting Eqn. (1) onto a reduced order basis T . This can be achieved introducing the change of coordinates

$$x = Tq, \quad (8)$$

where q is the vector containing the new set of generalized coordinates, and T is the reduced order basis. The new EOMs are obtained by introducing the change of coordinates and pre-multiplying by T^T as

$$T^T \hat{M} T \ddot{q} + T^T \hat{K} T q = T^T F, \quad (9)$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\hat{\mu} \ddot{q} + \hat{k} q = f, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{\mu}$, \hat{k} and f are the reduced order mass and stiffness matrices, and force vector. Writing the equations in the form presented in Eqns. (2)-(7) allows us to use single sector calculations when the EOMs are projected onto the reduced order space, resulting in faster calculations.

In this paper, the focus is on geometrically mistuned blisks, and in particular on those presenting blends. For this reason, the reduction method presented in [9] is used. The details of the method are omitted here for the sake of brevity (they can be found in [9]). The overall structure of the transformation matrix can be expressed as

$$T = [\Phi \ \Psi \ \Phi_{\text{BAM}}], \quad (11)$$

where Φ represents a set of pristine normal modes, Ψ represents constraint modes, and Φ_{BAM} represents blend acceleration modes (BAMs), which are typically very localized modes used to accelerate convergence. The MAX method is able to deal with large blends like the one shown in Figure 1b. When multiple blends, and thus multiple meshes, are used, the method requires the calculation of multiple sets of pristine modes. Hence, pristine modes need to be recalculated.

Figure 1: Blade meshes: a) Pristine un-morphed mesh. b) Blended mesh. c) Pristine morphed mesh.

METHODOLOGY

Matrices ${}_i\Phi^j$ and ${}_i\bar{\Phi}^j$ in Eqn. (6) can be obtained for each sector i with mesh j as a linear combination of two matrices of basis vectors ${}^n\mathbf{u}^j$ and ${}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$ as [7]

$${}_i\Phi^j = {}^n\mathbf{u}^j \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{N}(i-1)\right) - {}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j \sin\left(\frac{2\pi n}{N}(i-1)\right) \quad (12)$$

$${}_i\bar{\Phi}^j = {}^n\mathbf{u}^j \sin\left(\frac{2\pi n}{N}(i-1)\right) + {}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{N}(i-1)\right) \quad (13)$$

where n denotes the nodal diameter. Matrices ${}_i\Phi^j$ and ${}_i\bar{\Phi}^j$ are columns of matrices ${}_i\Phi^j$ and ${}_i\bar{\Phi}^j$. Please note that ${}^n\mathbf{u}^j$ and ${}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$ are single sector quantities that differ for each mode pair, each nodal diameter, and each mesh. Due to the symmetry of the system, a clocked (spatially rotated) version of an original mode pair is still a mode. Thus, cyclic modes computed independently for different meshes can present different clocking, as presented in Figure 2.

When multiple meshes are used, each mesh is typically associated with a set of modes, which could be clocked differently. To use such modes in the same model, consistency must be enforced, both in terms of interface compatibility and clocking.

Figure 2: Modes of the same blisk computed on different meshes that show different clocking.

The challenge of mode clocking can be solved using an approach similar to [7]. Clocking issues can be addressed by rotating the (misaligned) basis vectors ${}^n\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^j$ and ${}^n\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^j$ as to align them to the reference vectors, ${}^n\mathbf{u}^0$ and ${}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^0$ (computed for the reference mesh $j = 0$) to obtain an aligned basis ${}^n\mathbf{u}^j$ and ${}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$. Call ${}^n\phi^j$ the rotation angle between the two sets of vectors, which is different for each mode pair, each nodal diameter, and each mesh. The aligned vectors ${}^n\mathbf{u}^j$ and ${}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$ can be found as

$$\begin{aligned} {}^n\mathbf{u}^j &= {}^n\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^j \cos({}^n\phi^j) - {}^n\tilde{\bar{\mathbf{u}}}^j \sin({}^n\phi^j), & (14) \\ {}^n\bar{\mathbf{u}}^j &= {}^n\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^j \sin({}^n\phi^j) + {}^n\tilde{\bar{\mathbf{u}}}^j \cos({}^n\phi^j). & (15) \end{aligned}$$

The correct rotation to be applied can be found by maximizing the projection of the misaligned vectors onto the reference vectors as

$$\arg \max_{{}^n\phi^j} \frac{{}^n\mathbf{u}^0 \cdot {}^n\mathbf{u}^j}{\|{}^n\mathbf{u}^0\| \cdot \|{}^n\mathbf{u}^j\|}. \quad (16)$$

Every mode pair included in ${}^n\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^j$ and ${}^n\tilde{\bar{\mathbf{u}}}^j$ must be rotated by the appropriate angle. The alignment can be carried out using only one vector from the pair. The other vector in the pair is rotated by the same angle (with an adjustment factor of ± 1). In the results, this process is referred to as mode clocking. After clocking, the normal modes from different meshes are aligned, as shown in Figure 3.

The mode clocking method can be further refined by noticing that the modal projection can be carried out on a subset of nodes. If the subset with the largest motion is chosen, the dimensionality of the vector calculations in Eqns. (14)-(15) is reduced without sacrificing accuracy. For example, alignment can be done neglecting the disk nodes, which usually experience much lower levels of motion compared to the blades. Incidentally, this mapping is also useful when the node numbers are different and

some of the nodes are not co-located in different meshes. Nonetheless, the entire set of sector nodes is used in the results presented herein to ensure maximum accuracy.

The most significant drawback of the method presented in [7] is that it only clocks the modes without ensuring correct scaling and interface compatibility. In fact, the method does not change the maximum amplitude of the mode, which could be slightly different for each mesh, or the motion at the interface. To overcome this challenge, one can enforce the interface motion to be equal for nodes on matching surfaces at the interfaces between sectors, as suggested in [10], under the assumption that the differences in motion at the boundaries are small. Such interface nodes are shown in Figure 4. To preserve physical significance, the two sets of nodes on both sides of the interface must experience the same motion. Typically, interface compatibility is ensured by enforcing that the basis vectors applied to different sectors (which can be modes), present the same motion at the cyclic interface. This is automatically ensured for the vectors presented in Eqn. (6), but not for the ones presented in Eqn. (7). Modes in Eqn. (7) are obtained by stitching together sector-level pieces of modes calculated using different meshes in Eqns. (12)-(13).

Figure 3: Modes of the same blisk computed on different meshes that had different clocking (as shown in Figure 2) but they were re-aligned.

Let us consider the following partition of the modes of the i^{th} sector on mesh $m(i)$ (expressed with duplicate nodes on the interfaces between sectors)

$${}_i\hat{\Phi}^{m(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)} \\ \beta_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)} \\ \gamma_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

where the partition β represents internal nodes, while partitions α and γ represent nodes adjacent to the neighboring sectors (one on set of nodes for each side of the sector). The boundary α is adjacent to the sector having lower index, while γ is adjacent to the sector having higher index. Interface compatibility can be enforced by imposing

$$\gamma_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)} = \alpha_{i+1} \hat{\Phi}^{m(i+1)} \quad (18)$$

for all sectors. This method of ensuring common displacements at the interface is referred to as interface

compatibility. This method is applicable if mistuning is small, but it might not hold for larger structural variations, resulting in significant strains at the interface region.

Figure 4: Interface nodes between sectors, highlighted.

Pristine morphed mode extraction

The approach proposed in this paper to compute pristine morphed modes is based on the solution of a forced response problem instead of an eigen-analysis. In particular, the nodes with a one-to-one mapping on the original mesh are treated as boundary nodes forcing the structure motion. These nodes are forced to move along the un-morphed normal modes. The response is calculated for the remaining nodes. The calculation is carried out only on the morphed nodes, which in practical cases are much fewer than the total number of nodes of the entire sector, thus saving a substantial amount of computational time. The issue of scaling and cyclic interface matching is solved implicitly because the motion at the interface and at the matching nodes is imposed in the forced response calculation using the un-morphed normal modes.

First, the morphed mesh is mapped onto the baseline mesh, as shown in Figure 5c. In this step in the algorithm, all the nodes being co-located (overlapping between different meshes) are mapped. The nodes closer to the morphed region typically do not have a one-to-one mapping. Thus, the modal information must be recalculated for that region. The modes of the morphed mesh must be calculated to be consistent with the un-morphed modes. They should be clocked in the same way, have identical scaling, and be compatible at the cyclic interfaces. Furthermore, they should yield the same natural frequencies when used with their pristine morphed meshes.

Instead of recalculating the normal modes for each mesh, it is more convenient to compute them directly based on baseline modal information. Let us consider the EOMs for a pristine free-interface single sector with mesh j , i.e. the pristine sector without constraints on the motion at the cyclic boundaries. These EOMs can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{M}^j \ddot{\mathbf{x}}^j + \mathbf{K}^j \mathbf{x}^j = \mathbf{f}^j, \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{f}^j is a forcing vector applied to the sector. The vector of (response) physical degrees of freedom \mathbf{x}^j can be partitioned as

$$\mathbf{x}^j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_O^j \\ \mathbf{x}_D^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{x}_O^j is the vector containing the DOFs corresponding to the nodes of the morphed mesh that are overlapping the un-morphed ones, i.e. have a one-to-one mapping to the un-morphed baseline mesh $j = 0$, like the ones shown in Figure 5c. The vector \mathbf{x}_D^j contains the remaining DOFs from the morphed region, where the nodes are distinct from the un-morphed ones.

Figure 5: Mesh nodes for different meshes. a) Pristine un-morphed. b) Pristine morphed. c) Nodes that map (are the same) between the pristine morphed and the un-morphed meshes.

In the overlapping area, represented by \mathbf{x}_O^j , the modal motion obtained from the baseline calculation can be imposed. We can thus enforce $\mathbf{x}_O^j = \mathbf{x}_O^0$. The displacement of those nodes is the same no matter what mesh is used as long as the mesh is converged in the sense that the numerical discretized mode represents the physical mode. If the motion of the nodes identified as \mathbf{x}_O^j is imposed as a boundary condition, we can then solve for the remaining DOFs contained in \mathbf{x}_D^j . For that purpose, matrices \mathbf{M}^j and \mathbf{K}^j can be partitioned as

$$\mathbf{M}^j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{OO}^j & \mathbf{M}_{OD}^j \\ \mathbf{M}_{DO}^j & \mathbf{M}_{DD}^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K}^j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{OO}^j & \mathbf{K}_{OD}^j \\ \mathbf{K}_{DO}^j & \mathbf{K}_{DD}^j \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The EOMs in Eqn. (19) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{OO}^j & \mathbf{M}_{OD}^j \\ \mathbf{M}_{DO}^j & \mathbf{M}_{DD}^j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_O^j \\ \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_D^j \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{OO}^j & \mathbf{K}_{OD}^j \\ \mathbf{K}_{DO}^j & \mathbf{K}_{DD}^j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_O^j \\ \mathbf{x}_D^j \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_O^j \\ \mathbf{f}_D^j \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Note that vector \mathbf{f}^j is zero at all nodes that are not mapped (free nodes, namely $\mathbf{f}_D^j = \mathbf{0}$), and generally non-zero at all other nodes (constrained nodes). The motion of the DOFs included in \mathbf{x}_O^j is imposed and known (from the un-morphed mesh modes). Only one row of Eqn. (22) must be solved. Thus, Eqn. (22) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{M}_{DD}^j \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_D^j + \mathbf{K}_{DD}^j \mathbf{x}_D^j = \mathbf{f}_M^j + \mathbf{f}_K^j, \quad (23)$$

where \mathbf{f}_M^j and \mathbf{f}_K^j are the forcing terms coming from the contributions of the mass and stiffness terms due to the imposed time-dependent displacement at all mapped nodes. These forces can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_M^j = -\mathbf{M}_{DO}^j \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_O^j, \quad \mathbf{f}_K^j = -\mathbf{K}_{DO}^j \mathbf{x}_O^j. \quad (24)$$

Assuming harmonic motion at the natural frequency of the un-morphed modes, Eqn. (23) becomes

$$-\omega^2 \mathbf{M}_{DD}^j \mathbf{x}_D^j + \mathbf{K}_{DD}^j \mathbf{x}_D^j = \omega^2 \mathbf{M}_{DO}^j \mathbf{x}_O^j - \mathbf{K}_{DO}^j \mathbf{x}_O^j. \quad (25)$$

Since the terms in Eqn. (25) are not time-dependent, the equation can be readily solved for \mathbf{x}_D^j as

$$\mathbf{x}_D^j = (-\omega^2 \mathbf{M}_{DD}^j + \mathbf{K}_{DD}^j)^{-1} (\omega^2 \mathbf{M}_{DO}^j \mathbf{x}_O^j - \mathbf{K}_{DO}^j \mathbf{x}_O^j). \quad (26)$$

Since \mathbf{x}_O^j and ω^2 are derived from the un-morphed calculations, they will remain the same for all morphed meshes, while \mathbf{x}_D^j is re-calculated for each morphed mesh.

This procedure is presented in Eqn. (26) for every mode pair and for every sector. However, this can be accomplished using sector level calculations so that the calculation does not need to be done for each and all sectors, but only for a single sector. This is done by applying Eqn. (26) to the mode pair basis ${}^n \mathbf{u}^j$ and ${}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$ for all nodal diameters n which can then be expanded to obtain the morphed modes Φ^j and $\bar{\Phi}^j$ in all sectors. Thus, the mode pairs are partitioned for each mesh as

$${}^n \mathbf{u}^j = \begin{bmatrix} {}^n \mathbf{u}_O^j \\ {}^n \mathbf{u}_D^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad {}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}^j = \begin{bmatrix} {}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}_O^j \\ {}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}_D^j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

where ${}^n \mathbf{u}_D^j$ and ${}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}_D^j$ are calculated for every different morphed mesh, while ${}^n \mathbf{u}_O^j$ is enforced to be equal to ${}^n \mathbf{u}_O^0$ (for un-morphed mesh) and ${}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}^j$ is enforced to be equal to ${}^n \bar{\mathbf{u}}_O^0$. Thus, ${}_i \Phi^j$ and ${}_i \bar{\Phi}^j$ can be used instead of ${}_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)}$ and ${}_i \hat{\bar{\Phi}}^{m(i)}$ for the creation of $\hat{\Phi}$ and $\hat{\bar{\Phi}}$ without the need to clock them or to ensure interface compatibility, because both issues have been implicitly solved through the proposed mode extraction method.

In summary, the key idea of this approach is to use the overlapping nodes, shown in Figure 5c, to drive the motion of the other nodes at the natural frequency of the modes, and obtain the remaining part of the modes. This method is based upon a simple physical assumption: coincident nodes should have the same motion for a given mode even for different meshes, which holds when meshes are converged. Furthermore, since the natural frequencies of the pristine morphed system are the same as the un-morphed system, the forced response problem is solved at the natural frequency of the un-morphed mode.

Note that the proposed strategy ensures that the nodes at the cyclic boundaries move together. Also, from a computational cost standpoint, this technique represents a large gain, because morphing usually affects only a small portion of the entire mesh. The size of the forced response problem to be solved is thus small compared to the size of the entire sector.

Simplification of the projection

In the ROM creation, it is usually possible to simplify the calculations by invoking some of the properties of the basis vectors. For example, the method presented in [9] exploits the fact that when the pristine mass and stiffness matrices are projected onto normalized pristine modes, the projection assumes a very simple form. For a system having a single blend (i.e., a blend in a single sector), the ROM matrices calculated using [9] can be written as

$$\hat{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mu}_1 & \hat{\mu}_2 \\ \hat{\mu}_2^T & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{k}} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{k}}_1 & \hat{\mathbf{k}}_2 \\ \hat{\mathbf{k}}_2^T & \Lambda \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, and Λ is the (diagonal) eigenvalue matrix, which contains the squared natural frequencies ω^2 of the blisk.

The properties of the ROM matrices can be explained using the properties of the basis vectors in Eqn. (11). Recall that the modes of the system are orthogonal. Hence, for any pristine cyclic symmetric system one can write

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^{jT} \mathbf{M} \Phi^j &= \sum_{i=1}^N {}_i \Phi^{jT} \mathbf{M}^j {}_i \Phi^j = \mathbf{I}, \\ \Phi^{jT} \mathbf{K} \Phi^j &= \sum_{i=1}^N {}_i \Phi^{jT} \mathbf{M}^j {}_i \Phi^j = \Lambda. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

While Eqn. (29) holds with high accuracy for a system having a single mesh, it might not hold when modes computed for multiple meshes are used. Let us consider the case in which multiple pristine meshes are present. Consider that one mesh is the un-morphed one, and several others are morphed in different ways. Recall also that the modes contain duplicate nodes at the interfaces between sectors. This duplication allows one to use Eqn. (4) to describe the system matrices easily. Thus, one can write

$$\hat{\Phi}^T \hat{\mathbf{M}} \hat{\Phi} = \sum_{i=1}^N {}_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)T} {}_i \mathbf{M}^{m(i)} {}_i \hat{\Phi}^{m(i)}. \quad (30)$$

The sum above should theoretically yield the identity matrix. However, even though all sectors are pristine, the sum could differ when different meshes are present in different sectors. That is because the FE representation is

only an approximation of the physical blisk. This can result in the overall sum slightly deviating from the identity matrix. Thus, the identity matrix is not the most accurate to use in the ROM matrices in Eqn. (28). However, the entire projection does not need to be recalculated every time the mesh is changed. The new projection can be corrected. For example, let us consider for clarity a pristine system having a single pristine morphed blade (blade index $i = 1$, mesh type $j = 1$) while all the other blades are un-morphed, like the blisk shown in Figure 6. For the system with un-morphed meshes in all sectors, the following holds with high accuracy

$$\sum_{i=1}^N {}_i\Phi^{j^T} M^j {}_i\Phi^j = I. \quad (31)$$

For the system with a single morphed blade of blade index $i = 1$, the projection onto modes can be written as

$$\Phi^T \hat{M} \Phi = \sum_{i=2}^N {}_i\Phi^{0^T} M^0 {}_i\Phi^0 + {}_1\hat{\Phi}^{1^T} {}_1M^1 {}_1\hat{\Phi}^1, \quad (32)$$

where M^0 represents the mass matrix for the pristine un-morphed mesh, ${}_1M^1$ represents the mass matrix for the pristine morphed mesh, and ${}_1\hat{\Phi}^1$, ${}_i\Phi^0$ represent the modes of the pristine morphed and un-morphed mesh. Using Eqn. (31) with $j = 0$, Eqn. (32) can be re-written as

$$\Phi^T \hat{M} \Phi = I + {}_1\hat{\Phi}^{1^T} {}_1M^1 {}_1\hat{\Phi}^1 - {}_1\Phi^{0^T} M^0 {}_1\Phi^0. \quad (33)$$

By using Eqn. (33) in lieu of the full wheel projection the corrected ROM matrices can be calculated

$$\hat{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mu}_1 & \hat{\mu}_2 \\ \hat{\mu}_2^T & I + {}_1\hat{\Phi}^{1^T} {}_1M^1 {}_1\hat{\Phi}^1 - {}_1\Phi^{0^T} M^0 {}_1\Phi^0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (34)$$

$$\hat{k} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{k}_1 & \hat{k}_2 \\ \hat{k}_2^T & \Lambda + {}_1\hat{\Phi}^{1^T} {}_1K^1 {}_1\hat{\Phi}^1 - {}_1\Phi^{0^T} K^0 {}_1\Phi^0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The corrections in Eqn. (34) are computationally inexpensive because the size of the matrices is small. The sector level matrices K^0 and ${}_1K^1$ are N times smaller than the full wheel matrix \hat{K} . Thus, when an un-morphed sector is substituted with a morphed one, we can simply correct the projected matrices using Eqn. (34).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A numerical study is carried out to demonstrate the proposed approach for the blisk shown in Figure 7. The full model of this academic blisk has 516,733 nodes, and 1,550,199 DOFs. Two of the blades are blended, and one of them is morphed also. The pristine meshes of both morphed and un-morphed blades are shown in Figure 1. The MAX method is used as a benchmark to explore how mesh morphing can affect the accuracy of the ROM and to investigate the effectiveness of the new solution proposed. The results are presented both with and without blend acceleration modes (BAMs). The natural frequencies of the ROM are compared to those of the full order model, with the error e being defined as

$$e = \frac{|\omega_{ROM} - \omega_{FOM}|}{|\omega_{FOM}|}, \quad (35)$$

where ω_{ROM} and ω_{FOM} are the natural frequencies obtained using the ROM and the full order model. In this section, results with modes properly aligned/clocked are presented. Modes aligned incorrectly are not examined.

Figure 6: Pristine blisk with a morphed pristine mesh in one sector (sector 1).

Figure 7: Mistuned blisk with two blended blades, one of which is both blended and its mesh morphed.

Results obtained using interface compatibility techniques are presented in Figure 8. When the modes are not strictly enforced to satisfy the compatibility condition at the interfaces between sectors, the results are inaccurate if acceleration modes are used, as shown in Figure 8a. This means that the interface compatibility is not properly ensured through just mode alignment/clocking. In fact, the presence of additional basis vectors should improve the convergence when the correct matrices for the structure are used, but in this case they worsen it.

Since the formulation used to create the ROM is based on Eqn. (4), enforcing interface compatibility through the projection modes is crucial to capture the full wheel matrices correctly. Thus, it is important to ensure compatibility very accurately. If node pair compatibility at interfaces is imposed after alignment/clocking, as shown in Figure 8b, there is a general improvement in accuracy, in particular with acceleration modes. However, the accuracy without the acceleration modes remains compromised.

This occurs because the assumption of identical motion at the interface after alignment/clocking does not hold for highly morphed meshes. When the meshes are substantially different, their modes can have different scaling or different interface motion, which cannot be corrected effectively in a post-processing analysis. The physics of the problem must be invoked in the mode extraction phase to ensure compatibility and feasibility.

In contrast, the results shown in Figure 9 were obtained using the new method for alignment/clocking and mode calculation on different meshes. It can immediately be noticed that there is a substantial accuracy improvement both with and without BAMs. The new method calculates sector and interface motion at the same time, implicitly ensuring interface compatibility. Furthermore, the scaling of the modes is the same.

Figure 8: ROM vs FOM natural frequency comparison obtained using standard mode alignment/clocking and interface compatibility.

Figure 9: ROM vs FOM natural frequency comparison obtained using the new modal extraction method and correction applied to ROM matrices using Eqn. (34).

As explained in the previous section, the introduction of a new mesh makes it necessary to correct the normal modes projection used in the ROM construction. The results obtained without the correction of the projection are presented in Figure 10. The approach to align/clock the

modes and to ensure interface compatibility was used to obtain the solution shown in Figure 10a, while the new mode extraction method was used for the results shown in Figure 10b. In both cases the errors are very large, and numerical errors occur, especially when BAMs are used. That is because the ROM matrices were not adjusted. The correction in these matrices leads to the results in Figure 8b and Figure 9.

Figure 10: ROM vs FOM natural frequency comparison obtained without correcting the ROM matrices (i.e. without re-projection of the normal modes) for the approach based on mode clocking and interface compatibility as well as for the new calculation of the normal modes.

CONCLUSIONS

A novel method able to account for the presence of multiple meshes within reduced order models (ROMs) for cyclic structures was presented. The purpose of this method is to calculate the normal modes of the pristine morphed meshes and to investigate the effects that the use of multiple meshes have on the ROM.

The method is based on the solution of a forced response problem, and it acts on a reduced subset of nodes, corresponding to the morphed area. The formulation is simple and cost effective, without sacrificing accuracy. Furthermore, numerical issues associated with ROM creation when multiple meshes are used were considered, and a solution was proposed. The method was applied to the case of an academic blisk for validation, and it outperformed the methods that are currently available. The results highlighted that the accuracy of the method presented here is superior to the one offered by previous alignment/clocking approaches. In addition, numerical issues associated with the ROM creation due to the presence of multiple meshes were solved by means of a simple correction of the ROM matrices. The method could be used to reduce the computational cost in the calculation

of mistuned normal modes also. In fact, when small geometric mistuning is present, the forced response could appropriately capture the mistuned modes, further reducing the computational time and cost.

REFERENCES

- [1] Liu, W., and Yang, Y., 2007, "Multi-Objective Optimization of an Auto Panel Drawing Die Face Design by Mesh Morphing," *Comput.-Aided Des.*, **39**(10), pp. 863–869.
- [2] Van Der Auweraer, H., Van Langenhove, T., Brughmans, M., Bosmans, I., Masri, N., and Donders, S., 2007, "Application of Mesh Morphing Technology in the Concept Phase of Vehicle Development," *Int. J. Veh. Des.*, **43**(1–4), pp. 281–305.
- [3] Sieger, D., Menzel, S., and Botsch, M., 2014, "RBF Morphing Techniques for Simulation-Based Design Optimization," *Eng. Comput.*, **30**(2), pp. 161–174.
- [4] Vurputoor, R., Mukherjee, N., Cabello, J., and J. Hancock, M., 2007, "A Mesh Morphing Technique For Geometrically Dissimilar Tessellated Surfaces," *Proceedings of the 16th International Meshing Roundtable, IMR 2007*, pp. 315–334.
- [5] Staten, M. L., Owen, S. J., Shontz, S. M., Salinger, A. G., and Coffey, T. S., 2011, "A Comparison of Mesh Morphing Methods for 3D Shape Optimization," *Proceedings of the 20th International Meshing Roundtable*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 293–311.
- [6] Castanier, M. P., and Pierre, C., 2006, "Modeling and Analysis of Mistuned Bladed Disk Vibration: Current Status and Emerging Directions," *J. Propuls. Power*, **22**(2), pp. 384–396.
- [7] Baek, Seunghun, and Epureanu, Bogdan, "Reduced-Order Models of Blisks With Small Geometric Mistuning," *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics*.
- [8] Madden, A., Epureanu, B. I., and Filippi, S., 2012, "Reduced-Order Modeling Approach for Blisks with Large Mass, Stiffness, and Geometric Mistuning," *AIAA J.*, **50**(2), pp. 366–374.
- [9] Gan, Y., Mayer, J. L., D'Souza, K. X., and Epureanu, B. I., 2017, "A Mode-Accelerated XXr (MAX) Method for Complex Structures with Large Blends," *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.*, **93**, pp. 1–15.
- [10] Mbaye, M., Soize, C., and Ousty, J.-P., 2010, "A Reduced-Order Model of Detuned Cyclic Dynamical Systems With Geometric Modifications Using a Basis of Cyclic Modes," *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power*, **132**(11), pp. 112502-112502–9.
- [11] Tang, W., Epureanu, B. I., and Filippi, S., 2017, "Models for Blisks with Large Blends and Small Mistuning," *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.*, **87**, pp. 161–179.
- [12] Lim, S.-H., Castanier, M., and Pierre, C., 2004, "Vibration Modeling of Bladed Disks Subject to Geometric Mistuning and Design Changes," *45th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics & Materials Conference*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics.
- [13] Olson, B. J., Shaw, S. W., Shi, C., Pierre, C., and Parker, R. G., 2014, "Circulant Matrices and Their Application to Vibration Analysis," *Appl. Mech. Rev.*, **66**(4), pp. 040803-040803–41.
- [14] Thomas, D. L., 1979, "Dynamics of Rotationally Periodic Structures," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, **14**(1), pp. 81–102.
- [15] Van der Auweraer, H., Van Langenhove, T., Brughmans, M., Bosmans, I., Masri, N., and Donders, S., 2007, "Application of Mesh Morphing Technology in the Concept Phase of Vehicle Development," *Int J Veh. Des.*, **43**, pp. 281–305.